

GENRE CHARACTERISTICS IN THE ART OF TRADITIONAL SINGING

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Annotation: This article discusses reforms in the fields of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan, musical genres, traditional singing art, national status and its place in national music, genre features and performance methods in traditional singing art. detailed information is provided.

Keywords: music, genre, style, work, analysis, status, culture, art, direction, musical genre, performance, musicology.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, August 26, 2018 Resolution No. PD - 3920 “ On measures for innovative development of the arts ”, Resolution No. PD-4038 of November 28, 2018 “ On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, are becoming increasingly important.[1]

Genre and style are of great importance in the study of the law of general art, in music. Of course, a genre is a type. If we pay attention to its dictionary meaning, in French, genre means type, style. [2] In fact, the concept of genre is widely used not only in musicology, but also in literature, folklore, philosophy, Sufism and other fields. It is worth saying that in the genre, the structure, form, state of performance, conditions of performance, description of the performers, in what state and under what conditions the work is sung, what musical instruments are accompanied, and so on, must meet a number of specific characteristics. The genre contains the main elements of the musical language. In music, a genre is a generalization of one of its types. Another characteristic of the word genre is the meaning of “appearance”. Musical genres are types and forms of music that perform different functions. The concept of style is related to the emergence and development of music in certain historical and social conditions. [3] Each period has its own themes, music, and singing expressions according to its own and suitable conditions, environment, and situation, and their composers are mainly created by the people, moreover, by performing composers, and they belong only to that period. [4] Some genres that were created in the past periods, centuries, in their own time, will undoubtedly change in the next centuries or create a new look, be updated, and on the contrary, they may go out of public consumption. In this regard, style has a strong connection with all means of expression of music. Style is not only a term related to music, but we can also see this term being called based on other concepts in life. However, by connecting them directly with music, we have the opportunity to understand its essence more deeply.

Traditional Uzbek folk singing is a creative product of its own population. It has existed since very ancient times, and the harmony of voice, breath, instruments, and performance history have become very important in this performance. In the performance of traditional singing, it is customary for performers to sing individually, in pairs, in a group or in mass.

The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-3391 of November 17, 2017 on “Measures for the further development of the art of Uzbek national status” was announced.

In this decision, the art of maqom is defined as shashmakom, the classical music culture of the existing makom Uzbek-Tadjik rights in Uzbekistan, as well as the performance styles of the Khorezm maqom schools and Chormakom (Fergona-Tashkent) maqom schools. The art of national status, which is an integral part of the cultural heritage of our nation as a highly classical musical art, is highly valued, and with its ancient history, deep philosophical roots, unique artistic style and rich creative traditions, it is outstanding in our spiritual life. very documented opinions were expressed about the place.[5] In our opinion, it is time to give high value to our national statuses. Throughout the works, this unique art has been polished by the hard work and dedication, creative thinking of great poets and scientists, skilled composers, hafiz and musicians, and it is known and popular not only in our country, but also in the countries of the East and the world. The fact that “Shashmakom”, the crown jewel of the Uzbek-Tajik classical music art, was recognized by UNESCO as an intangible spiritual heritage of humanity and included in the Representative list shows how high this rare art is. Status works are status. It should not be equated with traditional singing works that are widespread among the population, but should be called with the term maqam, as it has been repeatedly emphasized above.

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